

Influence of Guidance and Counselling Services on Performance in Biology among Secondary School Students in Sokoto Metropolis, Sokoto State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

The study Influence of Guidance and Counselling Services on Students' Academic Performance in Biology among Senior Secondary Schools of Sokoto Metropolis. The population of the study comprises of male and female S.S. II students 2022/2023 session in selected secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis. This research work limited itself to five (5) selected senior secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis. The research adopted descriptive survey research design method of study during which self-questionnaire titled Influence of Guidance and Counselling Questionnaire (IGC-Q) was designed to solicit responses from the respondents. The instrument was validated by expert, while a reliability index of 0.85 was arrived at which considered the instrument adequate enough and reliable. Random sampling was used for selecting schools. Research adviser method was used for determining samples from the total population, three hundred and sixty four (364) sample of students of which were 245 male and 119 female sample of respondents were arrived at. Data collected was analyzed using simple frequency distribution table and the mean average. The findings revealed that, Guidance and counseling has significant impact on the academic performance of students in biology in secondary schools of sokoto metropolis through influencing their choice of biology as a subject, giving them orientation, influence their performance in biology as well as helps them towards achieving successful performance in biology. The study recommended that, Schools should ensure that their guidance and counseling offices are functioning effectively and also that qualified counselors are managing the offices. Schools should organize orientation services to both the teachers and students that will help improve their academic performance in all subjects.

Keywords: Guidance, Influence, Biology, and Academic Performance.

Introduction

The Nigerian educational system is progressively more and more complex. The Nigeria world is fast expanding and technological advancing daily affect both societal and individual lives in many perspective. The interesting thing is that the educational end is where the individual who selects a narrow and rigid educational route finds it more difficult to adjust or change when he gets to the vocational end. This is where educational guidance comes in and becomes useful in the first instance (Achebe, 2001). Guidance and counseling is a relatively new profession in the educational scene dating back to the late 1950, in Nigeria and 1906 in the USA where the profession first flourished (Sa'adiya, 2007).

Indeed few people in educational institutions and probably in the public sector see the need to introduce guidance and counseling in our school system which is a major force in the personal, social, educational and vocational development of students. It is also an integral, cost effective component of the talents and enhancing appropriate decision making. Hence, the federal government in Nigeria has recognized the necessity of guidance and counseling, this is in order to achieve the objectives of the national policy on education.

Sokoto state and its general populace recognized the importance of education since before independence. Therefore, the state was not left behind in the establishment of primary, secondary and tertiary institutions. Furthermore, for smooth facilitation, there is a state ministry of education and other related educational parastatals, charged with the responsibilities of

monitoring and evaluation of delivery of qualitative education in the state. Similarly, guidance and counseling unit was established within the ministry of education responsible for organizing and coordinating guidance and counseling services in all the secondary schools.

This development as well as the importance of guidance and counseling in the secondary schools sub-sector prompted the researchers to specifically undertake a study on the impact of guidance and counseling services in secondary schools in the state. This is with a view to address the adequacy, impact and perhaps observe some related problems and subsequently offer possible solutions and recommendations for improvement.

Despite the recognized importance of guidance and counseling in education, there is a lack of comprehensive understanding regarding the specific impact of guidance and counseling programs on students' performance in biology. While numerous studies have explored the influence of guidance and counseling on academic achievement, there is a need to specifically examine how targeted guidance and counseling interventions affect students' learning outcomes, attitudes, and motivation in the context of biology education. Furthermore, the specific mechanisms through which guidance and counseling contribute to improved performance in biology, including the role of student engagement, self-efficacy, and career aspirations within the field, remain relatively underexplored. Addressing these gaps is essential for developing evidence-based strategies to enhance students' performance in biology through effective guidance and counseling practices.

This statement highlights the need to investigate the specific impact of guidance and counseling on students' performance in biology, identifying existing gaps in the literature and emphasizing the importance of understanding the underlying mechanisms through which guidance and counseling interventions can influence students' academic achievement in this particular subject area.

The term guidance and counseling has been defined in various ways, by different authors. In this study, reference shall be made on some of these definitions as outlined below:

Guidance in common language involves personal help given by someone; it is designed to assist a person to decide where he wants to go, what he wants to do, or how he can best accomplish his purpose; it assist him to solve problems that arise in this life (Jones, 1940).

Shartzter and Stone (1980) was guidance as the process of helping an individual understand himself and his world. Okon, (1984) defines guidance as the total programme of a number of highly specialize activities implementation by specialist to help individuals make right chances and decision. Oladele, (1992) also saw guidance as aiming at aiding recipient to grow in his independence and ability to be responsible for him.

The above definitions concerned to Roger (2000) when he maintained that the purpose of guidance is to enhance the personal development and the psychological growth of clients towards socialized maturity.

Counseling on the other hand has been defined nu Makinde (2003) as a service designed to help an individual analyze himself by relating his capabilities, achievements, interest and mode of adjustment to what new decision he has made or has to make.

Ipaye (2003) saw counseling as a method of helping the individual utilize his or her psychological resources by focusing on that individual positive strength for development and by concentrating on the individual's personal behavior and emotional needs that could be mobilized.

Types of Counseling:

1. Individual Counseling: This is the counseling in which the counselor is involved with only one person and maintains confidentiality.
2. Group Counseling: This involves group of counselors from the definition given above, it can be seen that guidance is broad and aimed at assistant individuals to make and carry out adequate plans and to obtain satisfactory adjustment in life. While, counseling on the other hand is normally as one part or guidance services. It is sub-merged by the general term guidance in that it is one service within guidance. Counseling stresses rational planning problem solving remedial programs, thought, feeling and behavior evaluations, empathy, and verbal techniques, inter personal relationship and support in the face of situational pressures.

Due to the problems related with educational vocational pursuits, economical adjustment financial and industrial competition, interpersonal relations necessitated by increased human movement and exposure to the world of work and human interaction, moral issues associated with partner selection, disharmony and conflicts, culture and clashes as societal with trying to reconcile traditionalism and modernism; social demands and adjustment arising from changing social order and expectation, comes the need for professional guidance and counseling that will help people to strength their own abilities, to make nice and realistic decisions and chances adjustments and interpretations in connections with critical situation to life and face squarely

problems they may encounter in their daily existence. Hazes and Hopsor, (2000), Olayinka, (2002), Achebe, (2001), Okon, (1999) gave the major reasons why guidance and counseling sources are necessary in the country. The reasons are as follows:

1. The grouping needs of young people
2. Basic concerns and problems of students
3. Problem of national interaction
4. Social change and how it inflicts its grouping on children, youth and their families.
5. The need to develop and ensure skilled workforce.
6. Change in the family and home life
7. Increase enrolment in Nigeria educational institutions and the need to prepare for productive life.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are:

1. To find out how adequate guidance and counseling services are rendered among Government secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis.
2. To determine the extent of guidance and counseling services among Government secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis.
3. To assess the impact of guidance and counseling services on students' academic performance in Biology among Government secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis.

Research Questions

The following are the research questions:

1. How adequate is guidance and counseling services rendered among Government secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis?
2. What is the extent of guidance and counseling services among Government secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis?
3. What are the impact of guidance and counseling services on students' academic performance in Biology among Government secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis?

Significance of the Study

Study will help provide government with information about the availability or otherwise of guidance and counseling services in schools in Sokoto metropolis as well as the need of improving the services. Also, the findings of this study will help parents and guardians to have knowledge about the importance of guidance and counseling on the academic performance of their children in biology. Lastly, the findings of this study will serve as a road-map to future researchers who might want to conduct study on a similar topic.

Methodology

The research design used for this study was a descriptive survey research design. According to (Hussaini & Bello, 2023 in Torrentira 2020), a survey research design is the most common data collection technique in quantitative research. According to Dangal (2021), survey design is a means of gathering information about the characteristics, actions, or opinions of a large group of people and later uses a selected portion of the population from which the findings can later be generalized back to the population. The population of the study was 7,953 students which comprises male and female senior secondary school students in the Sokoto metropolis. They include both boarding and day secondary school students. There are twenty-two (22) public secondary schools in the area. The sample size selected was 364 comprised of 245 males and 119 females. A purposive sampling technique was used in selecting five senior secondary schools in the area and a proportionate sampling technique was used in selecting the participants from each selected school. Research Advisors (2006) table for determining sample size was used for determining the samples. A self-developed instrument titled "Influence of Guidance and Counselling Questionnaire (IGCQ)" was used as an instrument for data collection. The questionnaire was divided into two sections; section "A" consists of the demographic data of respondents, while section "B" involves questions that address the research questions. The instrument was a four Likert scale "Agree (A), Strongly Agree (SA), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD)". The content validity of the instruments was determined by experts in the Faculty of Education, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, and the reliability coefficient was determined through pilot testing of the instrument on non-participatory students in the Metropolis. The instrument reported a Cronbach's Alpha, coefficient of 0.85 which makes the instrument reliable enough to generate information for the study. Descriptive statistics specifically frequency and percentage count were used for results presentation.

Result

Research Question One:

How adequate is guidance and counseling services rendered among Government secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis?

Table 1. Adequacy of Guidance and Counseling Services in Secondary Schools of Sokoto Metropolis.

S/N	Items	Sample	SA		A		SD		D	
			F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1.	We have guidance and counseling unit in our school.	364	215	59%	100	27.4%	12	3.2%	37	10.4%
2.	Our teacher encourage us on the importance of guidance and counseling	364	101	27.7%	50	13.7%	102	28%	111	30.6%
3.	Our guidance and counseling unit is well equipped	364	17	4.6%	19	5.2%	211	58%	117	32.2%
4.	We have more than one guidance counsellor in our school	364	2	0.6%	7	2%	207	56.8%	148	40.6%
5.	Our head teacher serve as our guidance counsellor	364	106	29.1%	179	49.2%	7	2%	72	19.7%
6.	We are introduce to career guidance by our school counsellor on monthly basis	364	8	2.2%	16	4.4%	207	56.8%	133	36.6%
Total			20.5%		17%		34.1%		28.4	
Mean Average			37.5%				62.5%			

Source: Researcher Field Work (2023)

From table above, 215 respondents with 59% strongly agree on the statement that they have guidance and counseling unit in their school, 100(27.4%) agree while 37(10.4%) disagree and 12 (3.2%) strongly disagree. From item two, 111 respondents with 30.6% disagree that their teachers encourage them on the importance of guidance and counseling 102 (28%) strongly disagree while 101 (27.7%) strongly agree and 50 (13.7%) agree with the statement. Lastly, 211 respondents with the highest percentage of (58%) strongly disagree that their guidance and counseling unit is well equipped, 117(32.2%) disagree while 19(5.2%) agree and 17(4.6%) strongly agree. On the issue of whether head teachers serve as school guidance counsellors, 207(56.8%) of the students strongly disagree, 148 (40.6%) disagree while 7(2%) agree and only 2(0.6%) strongly agree that their head teachers serve as school guidance counsellors. In the fifth item, 179 respondents representing (49.2%) agree that they have more than one guidance counsellor in their school, 106(29.1%) strongly agree and 72(19.7%) disagree while 7(2%) strongly agreed with the statement. While 207 respondents representing (56.8%) strongly disagree that they are introduce to career guidance by our school counsellor on monthly basis, 133(36.6%) disagree with the statement while 16(4.4%) agree with the statement and 8(2.2%) strongly agree.

From the above data, the findings have shown that there is guidance and counseling unit in the secondary schools of sokoto metropolis. Teachers does not encourage their students to on the importance of guidance and counseling units in the secondary schools of sokoto metropolis were not equipped. Also, the school counsellors are not engaging in career guidance to help the students in appropriate career choice.

Research Question Two:

What is the extent of guidance and counseling services among Government secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis?

Table 2. Extent of Guidance and Counseling Services among Students in Secondary Schools of Sokoto Metropolis

S/N	Items	Sample	SA		A		SD		D	
			F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1.	I always patronize guidance and counseling unit in my school	364	10	2.7%	29	8%	106	29.1%	219	60.2%
2.	Whenever I have academic or personal social problem I go for counseling	364	14	3.8%	67	18.4%	77	21.1%	206	56.7%

3.	I hardly attend guidance and counseling	364	39	10.7%	262	72%	43	11.8%	20	5.5%
4.	Incompetency of our school counsellor discourages me from going for counselling	364	14	4%	13	3.6%	202	55.4%	135	37%
5.	Our school counsellor hardly have time to attend to our problems because of his/her busy schedules around the school	364	112	30.7%	198	54.3%	7	2%	47	13%
6.	I report only report problems related to learning to our school counsellor	364	19	5.2%	28	7.6%	149	41%	168	46.2%
Total				9.5%		27.3%		26.7%		36.5%
Mean Average				36.8%				63.2%		

Source: Researcher Field Work (2023)

Table 2 represents students level of utilizing guidance and counseling service. 219 respondents representing 60.2% disagree that they always patronize guidance and counseling in their school, 106 (20.7%) strongly agree, with the statement. Also, 206 respondents with 56.7% disagree that they patronize guidance and counseling when they have academic and personal problems, 77 (21.1%) strongly disagree while 67(18.4%) agree and 14(3.8%) strongly agree with the statement. Lastly, 262 respondents representing 72% agree that they hardly attend guidance and counseling service, 43(11.8%) strongly disagree while 39(10.7%) strongly service, 43(11.8%) strongly disagree while 39(10.7%) strongly and 20(5.5%) disagree with the statement. From the table also, 202(55.4%) strongly disagree that incompetency of their school counsellor discourages them from going for counselling, 135(37%) disagree with the statement, 14(4%) strongly agree that incompetency of their school counsellor discourages them from going for counselling, while 13(3.6%). 198 (54.3%) agree that their school counsellor hardly have time to attend to their problems because of his/her busy schedules around the school, 112 respondents representing (30.7%) strongly agree with the statement while 47(13%) disagree and 7(2%) strongly disagree that their school counsellor hardly have time to attend to their problems because of his/her busy schedules around the school. From the data above, 168(46.2%) disagree that they only report problems related to learning to their school counsellor, 149(41%) strongly disagree while 28(7.6%) respondents agree that they only report problems related to learning to their school counsellor and 19(5.2%).

Conclusively based on the above data, we can conclude that, students in the secondary school of sokoto metropolis does not patronize guidance and counseling service in their school. From all above data we can boldly say that there is lack of utilization of guidance and counseling service among students in the secondary schools of sokoto metropolis.

Research Question Three:

What are the impact of guidance and counseling services on students' academic performance in Biology among Government secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis?

Table 3. The impacts of guidance and counseling services on Secondary School students Academic Performance in Biology

S/N	Items	Sample	SA		A		SD		D	
			F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1.	My subject choice is influenced by my school counselor	364	197	54.1%	142	39%	3	0.8	22	6.1%
2.	My school counseling units gives us orientation from time to time on how to improve our academic performance in Biology	364	102	28%	218	60%	31	8.5%	13	3.5%

3.	My choice of biology as a subject is influenced by the guidance counsellor in our school	364	116	32%	201	55.2%	23	6.3%	24	6.5%
4.	My school counsellor provide solution to most of my learning problems especially in Biology	364	106	29.1%	157	43.1%	74	20.3%	27	7.5%
5.	Guidance and counselling services around my school helps in improving my academic performance in biology	364	207	56.8%	109	30%	11	3%	37	10.2%
6.	Through guidance services I was able to plan towards achieving successful grade in biology	364	106	29.1%	129	35.4%	39	10.7%	90	24.8%
Total				38.1%		44%		8.2%		9.7%
Mean Average				82.1%				17.9%		

Source: Researcher Field Work (2023)

From the above table, 197 respondents with 54.1% strongly agree that their school counselor influence their choice of subject, 142 (39%) agree while 22(6.1%) disagree and 3(0.8%) strongly disagree. Also, 218 (60%) respondents with the highest percentage agree that their school counseling units gives them orientation from time to time on how to improve their academic performance in biology, 102(28%) respondents strongly agree while 31 (8.5%) strongly disagree and 13(3.5%) disagree. Furthermore, 201(55.2%) agree that their choice of biology as a subject is influenced by the guidance counsellor in their school, 116 (32%) strongly agree while 24 (6.5%) disagree and 23 (6.3%) strongly disagree. From the table, 157(43.1%) agree that their school counsellor provide solution to most of their learning problems especially in biology, 106(29.1%) strongly agree with the statement while 74(20.3%) strongly disagree that their school counsellor provide solution to most of their learning problems and 27(7.5%) disagree with the statement. 207(56.8%) respondents strongly agree that guidance and counselling services around the school helps in improving students’ academic performance in biology, 109 respondents representing (30%) agree while 37(10.2%) respondents disagree that guidance and counselling services around their school helps in improving their academic performance in biology and 11(3%). 129(35.4%) agree that through guidance services they are able to plan towards achieving successful grade in biology, 106(29.1%) strongly agree while 90(24.8%) disagree that through guidance services they were able to plan towards achieving successful grade in biology, and 39(10.7%) strongly disagree with the statement.

From the data, we can say that guidance and counseling has significant impact on the academic performance of students in biology in secondary schools of sokoto metropolis through influencing their choice of biology as a subject, giving them orientation, influence their performance in biology as well as helps them towards achieving successful performance in biology.

Findings

Based on the data collected and analyzed the following findings were made with regard to the objectives of the study.

1. There is guidance and counseling service in secondary schools of sokoto metropolis. The unit’s exist even when they are not well equipped.
2. Teachers in the secondary schools of sokoto metropolis does not encourage their students on the importance of guidance and counseling services on their academic performance. Therefore, there is low patronage of the service.
3. Guidance and counseling has significant impact on the academic performance of students in biology in secondary schools of sokoto metropolis through influencing their choice of biology as a subject, giving them orientation, influence their performance in biology as well as helps them towards achieving successful performance in biology.

Discussion of Findings

1. The first finding has shown that secondary schools in sokoto metropolis establish guidance and counseling unit. The conclusion was made from data collected and interpreted in table 1 under item number one where by majority of the respondents with a frequency of 315 respondents representing (62.5%). The finding is in line with that of (Denga 2011), who highlighted that most secondary schools in state has residents’ guidance and counselor for sustainable entrepreneurship development.

2. Also, the finding have shown that students in secondary schools of Sokoto metropolis hardly utilize guidance and counselling services. That is to say there is lack of adequate utilization of guidance and counseling service among the students in secondary schools of sokoto metropolis. The conclusion was made based on the data collected in table 2 under item number one where the majority of the students with (63.2%) shows that they don't patronize the service. The finding have agreed with that of (Napier 2007) who says that poor attitude of teachers and non-cooperative attitude of students to the program is a major hindrance, depriving teachers does not encourage their students on the importance of patronizing the service.
3. Guidance and counseling has significant impact on the academic performance of students in biology in secondary schools of sokoto metropolis through influencing their choice of biology as a subject, giving them orientation, influence their performance in biology as well as helps them towards achieving successful performance in biology. The conclusion was drawn from table 3 where (82.1%) of the respondents testified to that. The finding is in line with the finding of (Borrow 2003) who said that it is a role of guidance and counseling program to provide students with necessary information about courses available, qualification, career aspiration as well as choice of subject.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were suggested:

1. Schools should ensure that their guidance and counseling offices are functioning effectively and also that qualified counselors are managing the offices.
2. School should make provision for career talk at least once in a year, which can be given by parents of pupil with different profession and staff members of the school.
3. Schools should organize orientation services to both the teachers and students that will help improve students' academic performance in all subjects.

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